

Semantics Based Compliance Solving

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Figure 1– The Proposed Solution for Semantics Based Compliance Solving

Present approaches to compliance solving have some shortcomings and suffer from some flaws and deficiencies, to name a few:

- # utilizing conventional logic solving
- # relying on restricted and a limited number of semantic models
- # a **reductionism** approach to semantics (results in “state space explosion”)
- # lack of a hierarchy of semantics
- # lack of semantic composition and combination

In order to resolving these issues, the proposed solution of this research is based on a network of semantics. For semantic compilation and building a logical and mathematical construction upon foundational semantics, we could utilize:

- # Logic (modal and deontic logics)
- # soft computing (particularly computing with words and perception-based computing)
- # Grammars
- # Reo circuits
- # and an occurrence-based semantics which is called “**Semantic Logic**”.

Semantic logic is an intuitionistic logic. Technically, it could be viewed as an axiomatic system on symbols with **Brouwer–Heyting–Kolmogorov Interpretation for semantics [1]**. It is sufficient to consider semantic logic consists of 1) a set of symbols (behalf of basic intuitions), and 2) a set of rules on them. Each rule describes a symbol generation action: when the left-side symbolic structure of the rule is ready in the working memory, the right-side symbolic structure is generated (See Figure 2) and pushed to the construction of symbols in the working memory (See Figure 3).

The manner and model of computation that is associated with semantic logic is similar to rewriting logics, generative grammars and the LISP programming language.

Figure 2- An example of a semantic logic rule and the effect of its application on working memory [3].

Figure 3– a semantic construction [3].

Sample Rule [2]:

$$\text{?}(O(A)) \wedge ((B \vee C) \rightarrow A) \rightarrow \text{!}(\text{?}(O(B)) \vee \text{?}(O(C)))$$

If (we require necessity of A) and (B or C yield A) then there is a choice for us to require necessity of B or necessity of C.

Example “Real World” Logic:

We are in hurry. Motorcycle and express taxi are two speedy vehicles. So there is a rational choice to consider motorcycle or express taxi.

References:

- [1] Masahiko Sato, "Classical Brouwer–Heyting–Kolmogorov interpretation." In Algorithmic Learning Theory, pp. 176-196. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 1997.
- [2] Mohammad Reza Besharati, Alireza Farhadi, Mohammad Izadi, “CABUTAR Framework for Intelligent Compliance-Solving Systems”, Proceedings of 8th International Conference on Information and Knowledge Technology (IKT2016), Hamedan, 2016.
- [3] Mohammad Reza Besharati, Mohammad Izadi, “DAST Model: Deciding About Semantic Complexity of a Text”, Technical Report, Disyslab, Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran, 2018.